

GROWTH, YIELD AND ECONOMICS OF SUGARCANE PLANTED THROUGH SINGLE EYE BUDDED SETTLING AS INFLUENCED BY NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT UNDER SOUTH GUJARAT CONDITION

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Abstract

An experiment was carried out during three consecutive cropping years of 2021-22, 2022-23 and 2023-24 at Main Sugarcane Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari to evaluate the effect of organic manure, biofertilizers in combinations with inorganic fertilizer on growth attributes, yield and economics of sugarcane (CoN 13072). The experiment consist of two levels of organic manure viz., 25 t/ha FYM (M₁), 15 t/ha bio compost (M₂): four levels of recommended dose of fertilizers 75% of RDF (F₁), 100% of RDF (F₂), 125% of RDF (F₃), 150% of RDF (F₄) and two levels of Bio-fertilizer viz., Without (B₁) and With bio fertilizers (Acetobacter + PSB+ KMB applied two times as basal and before final earthing up @ 2.5 l/ha each both time) applied to sugarcane planted through single eye budded settling replicated with three times in Factorial Randomized Block design. On the basis of pooled results of three years study, it can be concluded that growth, yield attributes and yield of sugarcane were not affected significantly due to different nutrient management treatments. Application of FYM@ 25 t/ha or bio compost 15 t/ha and application of fertilizer @188-94-94 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha with bio fertilizer were found superior for saving of 25 % fertilizer dose.

Keywords: Sugarcane, INM, FYM, Bio compost, Bio fertilizer, Cane yield

Introduction

Sugarcane is an important cash crop of South Gujarat and as such most of the sugarcane growers depend upon it for their cash requirements. Sugarcane occupies an area of 5.098 million ha with a production of 430.50 million tons having an annual average productivity of about 84.44 t/ha in India (Anonymous, 2022). Although India is the second largest producer of sugarcane and the highest consumer of sugar, productivity of the crop is low and cost of production is high resulting in low income of the 50 millions cane growers depending on sugarcane cultivation. During the year of 2024-25 in Gujarat State, area of sugarcane 189.60 thousand ha, production of sugarcane 13516.74 thousand tonnes and yield of sugarcane 71292 kg/ha (Anonymous, 2025). Sugarcane crop required 3-5 weeks to germinate and time of planting is most important for the farmers point as well as considering growth under specific environment requirement of the crop. Under the concept of Sustainable Sugarcane Intensification (SSI) techniques, use of settling as planting material is reported promising result with saving in the seed material and time for initial one month as well established settling use for planting. This will hold a great potential in boosting the national sugarcane production in a sustainable manner. Nutrient management is most important in high demanding sugarcane crop for better growth and economical production. To find out appropriate nutrient management for sugarcane planting through single eye budded settling this experiment was proposed.

Material and Methods

A field experiment was conducted during three consecutive cropping years, viz., 2021-22, 2022-23 and 2023-24 at Main Sugarcane Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari. The experimental site was located in Agro-Ecological Zone-III of South Gujarat Heavy Rainfall Zone. The soil texture can also be described as ranging from sandy clay loam to silty clay loam, medium in organic carbon, low in available nitrogen, low to medium in available phosphorus and high in potassium with 7.78 pH. The soil of the experimental sites is classified under the order "Inceptisols" according to the 7th Approximation, which

includes member of the fine, montmorillonitic, isohypothermic great soil group of Vertic Ustochrepts and soil series Jalalpur by the soil survey officer, Navsari, Department of Agriculture, Gujarat State (Desai and Patel 1970), having poor drainage capacity and good water holding capacity.

The experiment was laid out in Factorial Randomized Block design with three replications. The experiment comprised of two levels of organic manures viz., 25 t/ha FYM (M₁), 15 t/ha bio compost (M₂): four levels of Recommended dose of fertilizers 75% of RDF (F₁), 100% of RDF (F₂), 125% of RDF (F₃), 150% of RDF (F₄): and two levels of Bio-fertilizer viz., Without (B₁) and With bio fertilizers (B₂) (Acetobacter +PSB+KMB applied two times as basal and before final earthing up @ 2.5 l/ha each both time). Recommended dose of fertilizer (RDF) for Sugarcane is 250 N + 125 P₂O₅ + 125 K₂O kg/ha.

Sugarcane variety CoN 13072 was sown with spacing of 120 cm x 45 cm in December, 2020, December, 2021 and November, 2022 during the year 2021-22, 2022-23 and 2023-24, respectively. Sugarcane crop was harvested in the month of January, 2022, February, 2023 and February, 2024 during the year of 2021-22, 2022-23 and 2023-24, respectively. Sugarcane was fertilized as per treatments.

Results and Discussion

Effect on growth parameters

Pooled results indicate that effect of different treatments of integrated nutrient management on no. of tillers per plant at 60, 90 and 180 DAP and plant height (cm) at 180 DAP and at harvest were found non significant (Table 1 and 2).

It can be concluded that all the treatments of integrated nutrient management have equal effect on growth attributes. Similar findings were also reported by Bokhtiar and Sakurai (2007).

Effect on yield attributes and yield

On the basis of pooled results, effect of different treatments of integrated nutrient management did not show their significant effect on millable cane length, no. of millable canes at harvest, cane girth, no. of internodes

per plant, internodes length, single cane weight and cane yield (Table 3 to 5).

It can be concluded that all the treatments of integrated nutrient management have equal effect on yield attributes and yield. This corroborates with the finding of Kumar *et al.* (2017).

Effect on economics

The data (Table 6) indicate that higher net return (Rs.197376/ha) and higher benefit cost ratio (2.10) obtained due to application of manure under the treatment of M₁ (25 t FYM/ha).

Among the treatments of fertilizer application, higher net return (Rs.196064/ha) and higher benefit cost ratio (2.12) were recorded under the treatment of F₂-100 % RDF.

Among the treatments of Bio fertilizer application, higher net return of Rs.196719/ha and higher benefit cost ratio of 2.10 were recorded under the treatment of B₂- With bio fertilizer (Acetobacter +PSB+KMB applied two times as basal and before final earthing up @ 2.5 l/ha each both time).

The significant increase in economics under integrated supply of organic sources, biofertilizer alongwith adequate dose of inorganic fertilizers might be due to higher yield and low cost of cultivation of particular treatments. This results corroborates the earlier findings of Soomro *et al.* (2013) and Banerjee *et al.* (2018).

Conclusion

Based on pooled results of three year of experiment on "Effect of nutrient management on sugarcane planted through single eye budded settling" indicate that application of manure, fertilizer and bio fertilizer did not produce any significant effect in cane yield per hectare.

Application of FYM @ 25 t/ha or bio compost 15 t/ha and application of fertilizer @188-94-94 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha with bio fertilizer (Acetobacter +PSB+KMB applied two times as basal and before final earthing up @

2.5 l/ha each both time) were found superior for saving of 25 % fertilizer dose.

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Table 1. Number of tillers per plant/hill at 60, 90 and 180 DAP of sugarcane as influenced by different treatments (Pooled over three years)

Treatments	Number of tillers per plant/hill		
	At 60 DAP	At 90 DAP	At 180 DAP
Manure (M)			
M ₁ : 25 t FYM/ha	3.79	5.57	6.21
M ₂ : 15 t Bio compost/ha	3.78	5.62	6.19
S.Em±	0.05	0.07	0.08
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS
Fertilizers (F)			
F ₁ : 75% RDF	3.74	5.58	6.15
F ₂ : 100% RDF	3.76	5.59	6.18
F ₃ : 125% RDF	3.79	5.60	6.24
F ₄ : 150% RDF	3.83	5.61	6.22
S.Em±	0.07	0.10	0.11
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS
Bio-fertilizers (B)			
B ₁ : Without	3.78	5.57	6.19
B ₂ : With Bio-fertilizer	3.78	5.61	6.21
S.Em±	0.05	0.07	0.08
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS

Table 2. Plant height at 180 DAP and at harvest of sugarcane as influenced by different treatments (Pooled over three years)

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	
	At 180 DAP	At harvest
Manure (M)		
M ₁ : 25 t FYM/ha	198.4	328.60
M ₂ : 15 t Bio compost/ha	199.11	326.49
S.Em±	2.95	2.89

C.D. at 5%	NS	NS
Fertilizers (F)		
F₁: 75% RDF	196.14	325.42
F₂: 100% RDF	197.90	327.34
F₃: 125% RDF	200.52	330.33
F₄: 150% RDF	200.47	327.09
S.Em+	4.18	4.09
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS
Bio-fertilizers (B)		
B₁: Without	197.94	327.18
B₂: With Bio-fertilizer	199.57	327.90
S.Em+	2.95	2.89
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS

Table 3. Millable cane length, no. of millable cane per ha at harvest and cane girth of sugarcane as influenced by different treatments (Pooled over three years)

Treatment	Millable cane length (cm)	No. of millable cane/ha at harvest	Cane girth (cm)
Manure (M)			
M₁: 25 t FYM/ha	257.45	69194.55	8.86
M₂: 15 t Bio compost/ha	258.78	69380.32	8.88
S.Em+	2.93	842.19	0.07
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS
Fertilizers (F)			
F₁: 75% RDF	254.86	69364.23	8.85
F₂: 100% RDF	258.67	68575.99	8.84
F₃: 125% RDF	260.30	69299.28	8.89
F₄: 150% RDF	258.64	69910.25	8.88
S.Em+	4.15	1191.03	0.09
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS
Bio-fertilizers (B)			
B₁: Without	257.64	68655.98	8.88
B₂: With Bio-fertilizer	258.59	69918.88	8.86
S.Em+	2.93	842	0.07
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS

Table 4. No. of internodes per plant and internodes length at harvest of sugarcane as influenced by different treatments (Pooled over three years)

Treatment	No. of internodes/plant	Internodes length (cm)
Manure (M)		
M₁: 25 t FYM/ha	23.92	13.49
M₂: 15 t Bio compost/ha	24.20	13.53
S.Em+	0.09	0.09
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS
Fertilizers (F)		
F₁: 75% RDF	23.92	13.40
F₂: 100% RDF	24.10	13.42
F₃: 125% RDF	24.17	13.58
F₄: 150% RDF	24.04	13.63
S.Em+	0.13	0.13
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS
Bio-fertilizers (B)		
B₁: Without	24.07	13.46
B₂: With Bio-fertilizer	24.05	13.55
S.Em+	0.09	0.09
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS

Table 5. Single cane weight (Pooled of three years) and cane yield at harvest of sugarcane as influenced by different treatments

Treatment	Single cane weight (kg)	Cane yield (t/ha)			
		2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	Pooled
Manure (M)					

M₁: 25 t FYM/ha	1.50	103.54	120.32	92.63	105.50
M₂: 15 t Bio compost/ha	1.48	100.33	120.00	85.89	102.07
S.Em+	0.03	3.01	0.87	2.74	1.39
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Fertilizers (F)					
F₁: 75% RDF	1.47	95.33	118.79	87.74	100.62
F₂: 100% RDF	1.48	101.67	121.85	88.61	104.04
F₃: 125% RDF	1.52	101.75	119.44	91.03	104.07
F₄: 150% RDF	1.50	109.00	120.56	89.64	106.40
S.Em+	0.04	4.26	1.24	3.87	1.96
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Bio-fertilizers (B)					
B₁: Without	1.47	99.67	121.13	85.97	102.25
B₂: With Bio-fertilizer	1.52	104.21	119.20	92.55	105.32
S.Em+	0.03	3.01	0.87	2.74	1.39
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Table 6. Economics of different treatment.

Treatment	Cane yield (t/ha)	Gross return (Rs./ha)	Cost of cultivation (Rs./ha)			Net return (Rs./ha)	B:C ratio
			Fixed	Variable	Total cost		
Manure (M)							
M₁: 25 t FYM/ha	105.50	376635	139651	39608	179259	197376	2.10
M₂: 15 t Bio compost/ha	102.07	364390	139651	36580	176231	188159	2.07
Fertilizers (F)							
F₁: 75% RDF	100.62	359213	139651	30962	170613	188600	2.11
F₂: 100% RDF	104.04	371423	139651	35708	175359	196064	2.12
F₃: 125% RDF	104.07	371530	139651	40461	180112	191418	2.06
F₄: 150% RDF	106.40	379848	139651	45245	184896	194952	2.05
Bio-fertilizers (B)							
B₁: Without	102.25	365033	139651	36566	176217	188816	2.07
B₂: With Bio-fertilizer	105.32	375992	139651	39622	179273	196719	2.10